

**Analysing the Relationship between Gender Inequality and Economic Growth in
South America through the Presence of Gender Gaps in Education and Employment**

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Abstract

Using cross-sectional OLS and GMM regression, this study investigates how economic growth is affected by gender gaps in education and employment, specifically in South America. This relationship was investigated using a sample of 10 South American countries over a period of 20 years (2000-2020). Such inequality in education is found to negatively affect economic growth by 14.1% and this inequality in employment reduces economic growth by 8.6%. Generally, the richer countries in this region tend to see a higher gender equality within education, whilst the poorest see more of this equality within employment. Using quantile regression it was found that the gender gap in education has a stronger relationship with GDPPC amongst richer countries, whilst the gender gap in employment is more influential on GDPPC amongst the poorer countries.

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1. Introduction

Gender inequality is of increasing importance globally and it is goal five of the sustainable development goals (United Nations, 2015). By encouraging female participation in school and work, a more sustainable economic output is thought to be achieved, as this equality is linked to development in a sustainable way (2030 Agenda in Latin America and Caribbean, n/d). However, gender inequality persists across the world with women contributing only 37% to GDP despite making up 50% of the global population (McKinsey Global Institute, 2015). In the Latin American region, women contribute to only one third of total GDP for the region.

Throughout the decades, a lot of attention has been paid to how education and employment affect economic growth. However, less attention has been paid to the influence of gender inequality within education and employment on economic growth. While some studies have been conducted on the impact of gender inequality on growth, many have looked at gender inequality using indices constructed by various organisations, such as United Nations, rather than considering the specific benefit of an equally qualified population and gender-equal workforce.

To further this, little work has been carried out on South America as a region. Koengkan et al (2022) look at the Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) region and determine that a higher level of gender equality leads to higher growth, using the gender inequality index (GII) and OLS and fixed effects regression. The GII is made up of three aspects; reproductive health (measured using birth rates and mortality of mothers); females' education and political participation (using female owned parliamentary seats and the proportion of females and males with secondary education); and economic contributions (measured using male and female labour force participation rates). LAC has been ranked the 3rd most gender equal region in the world, according to World Economic Forum (2022), following North America and Europe but despite this, it is predicted it will take another 67 years before the gender gap in this region is closed. Governments in some Latin American countries have so far focused on policies that eradicate violence against women and help women to maximise their rights, however, they have not yet looked at encouraging gender equal accesses to education and the labour market, with female unemployment

ranking significantly higher than that of males (2030 Agenda in Latin America and Caribbean, n/d).

The recent empirical findings discover that there is a relationship between economic growth and gender inequality, as well as specifically for gender differences within education and employment and there is evidence that if men and women were completely equal globally then global GDP could increase by 26% per year (McKinsey Global Institute, 2020). However, the results have been mixed. Whilst most studies have found that improving gender equality in education (Klasen, 2002; Dollar and Gatti, 1999) and employment (Baerlocher et al, 2021; Ghosh and Ramanyake, 2018) leads to economic growth, some have found the opposite to be the case (Seguino, 2000). Furthermore, some work has been carried out looking at the reverse relationship, finding an increase in growth leads to greater gender equality in education and employment (Dollar and Gatti, 1999; Forsythe, Korzeniewicz and Durrant, 2000).

This thesis aims to understand the relationship between gender gaps in education and employment and economic growth in South America and is divided into seven sections, the first section being the introduction. The second section is the literature review which summarises the findings and methods of previous empirical studies in the field. The third section explains the method used and the sources and uses of data included in the model. Section four shows the preliminary findings and an initial description of the results followed by understanding the findings of the OLS, quantile and GMM regressions undertaken. The final section will conclude this study.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Gender Inequality and Economic Growth

As well as Koengkan (2020); Bertay, Dordevic and Sever (2020) among others also use a GII to measure gender equality and discover a positive relationship between gender equality and economic growth. An interesting aspect about this study is that to measure economic growth they show that industries with a high share of female labour grow faster in countries which are gender equal, based on GII. Unfortunately, this study is not without its limitations. Due to data accessibility, this study is limited solely to the manufacturing sector for certain countries and uses a sample of developing countries to conclude a result which is assumed to apply to all countries.

In their review of the literature, Bandiera and Natraj (2013) use a cross country study which determines that females lag in political and economic participation and that this has hindered growth. Furthermore, their study highlights the difficulties with using a GII and other gender equality measures as a variable because there are a large variety of factors that determine gender inequality, and the measurements of these variables can differ from country to country. In addition, Slotsky et al (2016) discuss the benefits and drawbacks of composite indicators such as the Gender Development Index (GDI) and GII in their work. They state that each index is composed of a different weighting, aggregation and combination of indicators which leads to unreliable comparisons. This research suggests a drawback to the studies that use a gender inequality index. The literature focusing on gender equality indicators and gender gap data to establish a relationship with economic growth is reviewed next.

2.2 Gender Gap in Employment and Economic Growth

Pennings (2022) creates an index called Gender Employment Gap Index (GEGI) which measures the effect of closing the gender gap in employment on economic growth, focusing specifically on the Pacific Islands. This index, calculated using a measure for female, male and total employment, is correlated with economic growth and their results show that long run GDP per capita would see an average

increase of almost 20% if gender gaps in employment were closed by bringing female employment up to that of males. This paper proves that this index (which is considered basic as it does not control for anything except labour force participation) has a correlation of 97% with the full-GEGI, where full-GEGI controls for differences in high and low wage employment. This study is useful in terms of showing directly how the index works as well as showing that a reduction in gender employment gaps is related to economic growth. However, due to its primary focus being the index creation, it does not use any econometric techniques and so cannot test causality. Building on the work of Pennings (2022), this study uses this index to examine the effect of the gender gap in employment on economic growth.

Looking at the female labour force participation rate and its impact on economic growth, Baerlocher et al (2021) uses data from 1980 to 2005 and determines that growth in the female labour force participation can positively impact growth. As females work more, total labour force participation increases which can increase output and economic growth (Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco, 2007). Adding to this, allowing women and men to access the labour force equally means the economy has a larger pool of workers to choose from (McKinsey Global Institute, 2015), reducing the likelihood of labour shortages and encouraging innovation and competition which creates sustainable economic growth. The Baerlocher et al (2021) study uses panel data for a sample of 100+ countries and uses a Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) estimator and dynamic model of a per capita production function (Baerlocher et al, 2021). However, it cannot conclude that the discovered relationship is specifically due to an increase in females or an increase in the labour force.

However, a study by Seguino (2000) finds a negative relationship. It looks at economic participation of females and their influence on economic growth, with a focus on 20 semi-industrialised predominantly-export countries from 1975-1995 and discovers a positive relationship between gender inequality and growth in exports and investment within certain economies, including Brazil, Chile, Colombia, and Paraguay. As the paper focuses on export-oriented countries, they conclude that a reason for this impact is because lower female wages lead to lower costs of

production. However, in a gender study it can be limiting to only focus on wage differences as it does not consider the differing hours worked in paid lines of work compared with domestic work, therefore labour productivity is not considered. A study carried out by Schober (2011), to further this research, uses wage discrimination data and like Seguino looks at export orientated developing countries over the same period. Included in Schober's study in addition to Seguino's work, is hourly wage rate and hours worked, allowing the analysis to consider the productivity of each gender.

2.3 Gender Gap in Education and Economic Growth

Klasen (2002) found that improving gender equality leads to increased economic growth due to improved human capital, for 1960-1992, using cross-sectional regression for regions of the worlds. Unfortunately, Klasen's study is unable to prove a causal relationship between gender equality and economic growth, potentially due to omitted variable bias. The study uses PPP-adjusted income and growth per capita as its dependent variable, controlling for investment rates, trade openness and population growth. In terms of education, he includes years of schooling as well as female working age population data. In his analysis he studies the direct and indirect effects of gender inequality on growth. Klasen (2002) theorises that gender gaps in education exist because more males participate in education than females. By assuming that the population is made up equally of males and females, the presence of gender gaps suggests there are women who are not as educated as others. In terms of education, this suggests that the average human capital is lower than it would be if everyone was as educated as each other which would therefore increase Gross Domestic Product per Capita (GDPPC). Improvements in education lead to improvements in employment. As productivity increases in household and parental tasks, improving education could then lead to an increase in labour force participation as individuals are able to spend less time in the household and more time in formal employment. Also, on average returns to female education are higher than that of males (Patrinos, 2008; Hill and King, 1995), and the less developed the country, the higher the returns. These higher returns to education are translated into higher wages which likely leads to an increased female labour force

participation rate as the opportunity cost of not participating increases (IZA World of Labor, 2016). One limitation to the work carried out by Klasen is that to address simultaneity he uses instrumental variable regression using fertility and education spending as his instruments. Although, Klasen claims these pass the relevancy and exogenous tests, it seems unlikely as fertility is shown to be a determinant of economic growth (Dollar and Gatti, 1999). In addition, participation in education appears to have become more equal since Klasen's (2002) study was undertaken and even begun to favour females (UNESCO, 2020). Thus, this thesis contributes to the literature by providing an updated view on the relationship by studying more recent time periods.

A study by Dollar and Gatti (1999) finds similar results to that of Klasen; that income and female secondary school achievement are positively related. Their reasoning for using the secondary school achievement variable is based on previous growth-related literature as it was discovered to be a significant measure of gender inequality and a good explainer of growth. The sample covers many countries and using a basic panel growth regression adapted to include female and male secondary achievement separately as well as fertility. The findings of this show a weak positive coefficient for female education, a weak negative for male and a large negative result for fertility. Thus, they conclude that female education can lead to a reduction in fertility and population growth which contributes to increased income per capita. As shown fertility and population are found to be determinants of economic growth, so are included as controls in this study. In their paper, they also look at the influence of economic growth on gender inequality suggesting potential endogeneity issues. To circumvent the problem of reverse causality, Dollar and Gatti (1999) use variables related to religions and freedoms as instruments for gender equality and run a two-stage least squares regression as well as a basic OLS regression. As data for these variables is not available for the countries and periods in my study, to avoid the reverse causality issue I will use a GMM estimation, like Baerlocher et al (2021) and Cabeza-Garcia, Del Brio and Oscanoa-Victorio (2018).

Using a ratio for average school years of women compared to men, Thenevon and Salvi del Pero (2012) avoid the endogeneity problem by using a long panel and

including lagged values for the explanatory variables. However, they state that this does not entirely mitigate the problem as there is still some potential that the error term could be correlated with economic growth. They find that when access to education is provided equally, economic growth increases. Unfortunately, they did not identify the causes but suggested that one explanation could be decreasing but complementary returns. It is believed that a higher level of gender equality in education means women have a greater understanding of healthcare allowing children to grow up healthier (Hill and King, 1995). In various studies, it has been found that an educated mother leads to better children's nutrition and physical growth, which increases their learning capabilities and in turn improves human capital of the younger generation. This higher level of human capital of future generations leads to increased sustainable economic growth.

Conversely, Barro and Lee (1994) find in their research on economic growth sources that lower initial female educational attainment is correlated with high growth. When adding initial female education and male education separately into their basic regression for growth, the coefficient for female is negative. Their suggested explanation for this is that a large difference between female and male educational attainment is an indicator for poor economic development. Furthermore, in their previous 1993 study they found that overall both female and male years of education have positive effects on economic growth. Although, Barro and Lee do not find that gender gaps in education cause economic growth, they can determine there is a positive effect of both males' and females' education on growth. However, as highlighted by Kabeer and Natali (2013) this study was not corrected for multicollinearity, therefore the individual effects of female and male education cannot be properly assessed.

2.4 Gender Gap in Education and Employment and Economic Growth

Finally, looking at the effect of both variables together on economic growth, a study by Cabeza-Garcia, Del Brio and Oscanoa-Victorio (2018) shows that economic growth is positively related to female access to further education, employment and political participation, while high fertility is related to lower growth. They use a 2-panel system GMM approach allowing the research to control for heterogeneity and

exogeneity, using data from 2000-2014 for 127 countries. This method requires four consecutive years of data per country. They also use inclusive economic growth as their dependent variable as defined by the total value derived from all members in an economy, with an emphasis on all. One possible shortcoming of their study is that they used proxies for certain variables where data wasn't available, for example when they considered there to be crises, they gave a dummy variable 1 and 0 otherwise. As the period in this thesis (2000-2020) also covers crises periods, to ensure these crises have been considered, country and time Fixed Effects (FE) will be controlled for, instead of using a dummy variable. Also, to assess whether the crises periods covered in this study alter the relationship between gender equality and economic growth, in section 4.3.2 the periods affected by crises are analysed in isolation.

An alternative measure to looking at gender gaps in education and employment is to use Global Gender Gap Index (GGGI), as carried out by Ghosh and Ramanyake (2018). This index includes economic participation, educational attainment, and political and health outcomes. Using an OLS and GMM approach to ensure robustness, they conclude that an increase in the index, thus a reduction in the gender gap, has a positive effect on economic growth in low-income countries. On the other hand, this has a negative effect on OECD countries, this result was not significant when controlling for export growth (a robustness check), which allows them to conclude for high-income countries gender gaps are not an important factor for growth. However, using GGGI as a method of measuring gender gaps in employment and education has drawbacks in fully answering the question, and therefore will not be used in this study. This is because there is no way to distinguish between which of the included factors are influencing the gender gap.

A study by Forsythe, Korzeniewicz and Durrant (2000) looks at the reverse relationship of how improved economic growth influences women's place in society. For the dependent variable they used the Gender Development Index (GDI), developed by the UN. The issues with this as a variable measuring inequality have been outlined above. But, instead of looking solely at how economic growth influences GDI, they divided it to run separate regressions looking at the education,

income, and life expectancy components individually. They concluded that there is a strong linear relationship between an increase in economic growth and the status of women, using data from 1992 for a variety of countries. Although this paper does not look at gender inequality specifically through gaps in education and employment, it can conclude that as gender equality in income and education improves, GDPPC increases. Furthermore, this paper includes Latin America as a dummy variable, as they expect that this region is subject to inherent inequalities. However, they find that this variable was not significant when looking at the education and income components of gender inequality.

While many authors have analysed the influence of either a gender gap in education or employment on economic growth there is little work that has focused on the two in tandem. In terms of South America, while Koengkan et al (2022) looks at how gender inequality affects economic growth in Latin America, using an index. There has been little work on South America from the perspective of gender gaps specifically in employment and education. Due to the drawbacks of using an index, this research will help to determine whether the presence of gender inequality in South America impacts economic growth. From my review of the existing empirical literature, I have formed the following hypotheses that a reduction in the gender gap in employment (hypothesis one) and education (hypothesis two) leads to improved economic growth.

Hypothesis One: A reduction in the employment gender gap leads to improved economic growth.

Hypothesis Two: Reducing the educational gender gap leads to improved economic growth.

3. Data and Methodology

3.1 Data

The sample includes data for 10 South American countries: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay, and Venezuela. Initially, Guyana and Suriname were included in the sample to cover the South American continent. However, due to poor data coverage for both independent variables as well as some control variables, it was decided they would be excluded from the study to avoid excess noise. The period studied from 2000-2020 gives an updated perspective on some of the work that has already been addressed in the existing literature.

Klasen (2002) highlights that a measurement problem can arise when looking at economic growth and gender inequality, especially in the developing world. This is because many of the tasks such as household and parental tasks that mostly females undertake are not included in national accounts and not therefore recorded in the data. McKinsey Global Institute (2015) also highlights that women add the equivalent of an extra 13% of GDP in economic value based on household or parental tasks which is not considered in GDP figures. Women are recorded to do on average 75% of all unpaid tasks globally, including cooking, cleaning and child rearing; meaning they have less time to work. Therefore, findings may not truly represent the relationship between gender inequality in education and employment and economic growth.

This study takes data from the following sources, with the data issues in mind.

Data on economic growth, the dependent variable, is based on GDP per capita (current US\$) for the period 2000-2020. Taken from World Bank National Accounts Data GDP (World Bank, 2022a) is divided by population (World Bank, 2022b) and converted to logarithm form. Taking the natural logarithm allows it to be normally distributed and therefore, a better fit for OLS regression. This follows the works of other researchers (Thenevon and Salvi del Pero, 2012).

The variable for employment gender gaps uses female, male and total Labour Force Participation Rate for 2000-2020. Data is modelled by the International Labour Organisation (ILO) to provide comparable statistics. This is a widely used method

that includes nationally reported and imputed data for missing values (ILO, n/d) and has been taken via World Bank (2020c). This was chosen as an indicator as it considers those in work as well as those searching for work. The gender gap has been constructed, using the same method as Pennings (2022):

$$LFPR\ Rate = \frac{Male\ LFPR - Female\ LFPR}{Total\ LFPR} \quad (1)$$

The variable for education gender gaps uses educational attainment for males, females, and total population from 2000-2020, measured as the percentage of individuals that completed at least upper secondary, for all those aged 25 and above. This data is taken from UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2020). Some data for these variables is not available for certain years in certain countries. This was the chosen indicator because, although it has the potential to be affected by measurement error it is less likely to be affected than alternative indicators, for example years of schooling, as it is simply the percentage of people that have at least completed upper secondary. The gap has been constructed as:

$$Schooling\ Rate = \frac{Male\ educational\ attainment - Female\ educational\ attainment}{Total\ educational\ attainment} \quad (2)$$

Other data points used as controls in the models include fertility rate (World Bank, 2020d), exports (World Bank, 2020e), and population (World Bank, 2020b). These are used as they have been found to influence economic growth. Falling fertility rates have been found to improve GDP (Ashruf, Neil and Wilde, 2012) and population growth is found to reduce productivity and economic growth (Bucci and Prettnner, 2020). In terms of exports, Feder (1983) and Ghosh and Ramanyake (2018) find that improvements in exports and export sector productivity lead to higher economic growth. Also, education expenditure is taken from UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2020) and is measured as government expenditure on education as a percentage of GDP. Finally, a lot of time was spent searching for data on the informal

sector as it employs a large portion of the South American population, particularly women (Draper, 1985) but unfortunately there was no data available.

3.2 Summary Statistics

Table I shows the summary statistics for the variables that will be used in the model. As shown, there is less observations for SchoolingRate, due to missing data points for a few years during the period for a few different countries. For example, for years 2000 and 2002 there is no data for any country and for 2001, data is included only for Argentina and Bolivia which has skewed the datapoint due to Bolivia's higher than average gender gap. Education Expenditure is also missing a few data points for certain countries and certain years. Other variables slightly affected by missing values are GDPPC and exports which are missing the last six years of data for Venezuela only. Finally, labour force participation rate is up to date up until 2019 for all countries, but missing data for 2020. Table A1 explains each variable and their measurements in more detail.

Table I: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for each Variable, 2000-2020

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
GDPPC (\$)	204	6845.987	4391.14	888.199	18825.28
SchoolingRate	107	-0.010	0.129	-0.259	0.307
LFPRRate	200	0.347	0.094	0.134	0.630
Fertility	210	2.396	0.488	1.611	4.059
Exports (% GDP)	204	25.982	9.724	10.188	47.594
Education Expenditure (% GDP)	165	4.437	1.470	1.151	9.837
Population	210	39,100,000	54,200,000	3,292,224	213,000,000

Notes: Data on 10 South American countries Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Paraguay, Peru, Uruguay, and Venezuela, over the period 2000-2020.

On average, for the sample studied, the LFPRRate is positive while the SchoolingRate is negative, meaning as a region there is gender based inequality

within education and employment, however, employment inequality favours males while education inequality favours females. The mean *SchoolingRate*, -0.010, suggests that on average South America as a region is relatively gender equal within education. This provides an updated finding to that of Klasen (2002), who found that women were on average less educated than men. For *LFPRRate*, the minimum is 0.134, so in every country and in every year, women participate less in the labour force than men. This initial finding is of interest as it suggests that despite more females having a secondary school education than males they are still less employed than males, thus we can assume the region is inefficient and firms are not employing the most skilled or educated workers.

Both the *SchoolingRate* and the *LFPRRate* have a small standard deviation meaning that across all countries and years there is not a huge variation in the gender gaps. This suggests that the countries are relatively similar and that there has not been too much improvement to gender equality over the period studied.

3.3 Methodology

Firstly this study explored the descriptive results provided by the data, looking at the correlation between the gender gap variables and economic growth both over time and across countries.

This study then used pooled cross-sectional OLS regression controlling for country and time Fixed Effects (FE) as the main model.

The econometric specification used is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \log GDP_{nt} = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 SchoolingRate + \beta_2 LFPRRate + \beta_3 Fertility + \beta_4 Exports \\ & + \beta_5 \log(pop) + \beta_6 EducationExpenditure + x_n + v_t + \varepsilon_{nt} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In the above equations, β_0 represents the intercept term, ε_{nt} represents the error term and x_n represents country FE (across n countries) while v_t represents time FE (for t years). Also, robust standard errors are used to allow for heteroskedasticity biasedness and autocorrelation.

Following this, to determine whether there is some form of heterogeneity across certain periods of interest i.e. periods of economic downturn, OLS regression

was performed for those specific periods. To assess heterogeneity across countries, quantile regression was used. This allows us to determine whether the influence of gender gaps on economic growth differ depending on whether a country is rich or poor. This can in turn help to guide policy decisions. Due to a small sample size, terciles were used.

Given that the data to be studied is macro level data, it is important to consider the potential endogeneity problems that may occur (Thenevon and Salvi del Pero, 2015). It is likely that as a country grows and becomes more developed the level of education and human capital will increase, as shown in the research by Dollar and Gatti (1999). The same is likely to occur for gender-based employment equality as a country becomes more developed. The control variables for fertility, population, exports, and education expenditure are included in the model in an attempt to mitigate these reverse causality issues as they help to isolate the effect of the gender gaps in education or employment (Woolridge, 2010). Furthermore, the inclusion of FE eliminates any time invariant country or time effects that are common across all countries. However, there is still potential for endogeneity to occur in the form of reverse causality.

To mitigate this issue in the best way possible, this study uses GMM estimation, similarly to Baerlocher et al (2021), Ghosh and Ramanyake (2018) and Cabeza-Garcia, Del Brio and Oscanoa-Victorio (2018). GMM regression allows for reverse causality as well as any unobserved heterogeneity to be considered and controlled for and allows for the identification of causal links (Ullah, Akhtar and Zaefarian, 2017). According to Ullah, Akhtar and Zaefarian (2017) in a GMM study, typically two lags of the independent variable are used because from that it is considered possible to analyse the persistence of the dependent variable, in this case GDPPC. Such researchers that use this method are Schultz, Tan and Walsh (2010) and Wintoki, Linck and Netter (2012). The following specification is used where the one and two period lagged values of logGDPPC is included in the regression.

$$\begin{aligned} \log GDPPC_t = & \beta_1 \log GDPPC_{t-1} + \beta_2 \log GDPPC_{t-2} + \beta_3 \text{SchoolingRate}_t + \beta_4 \text{LFPRRate}_t \\ & + \beta_5 \text{Fertility}_t + \beta_6 \text{Exports}_t + \beta_7 \log(\text{pop})_t + \beta_8 \text{EducationExpenditure}_t + \varepsilon_1 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The lag of the dependent variable, often called an internal instrument when included in the regression equation, removes the time-invariant FE by including the lag of the dependent variable (Ullah, Akhtar and Zaefarian, 2017). Once the model has been estimated, to ensure its appropriateness the Sargan test and the Arrellano-Bond test will be checked to ensure the result is valid.

Finally, to check the robustness of the study, the OLS regression is rerun using a different measure for constructing the gender gap in education and employment as well as a different measures for economic growth. Robustness will be assumed if, when using these different measures to conduct the same OLS regression, the relationship between the variables of interest (gender gap in education and employment variables and economic growth variables) yields a similar relationship and significance.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive Results

Figure I displays the Male and Female trend in terms of LFPR and Upper Secondary Completion Rate individually. The female LFPR is lower than male for all years by around 30%. However, over the period this gap closed slightly, with male LFPR slightly falling and female LFPR increasing throughout. Although, there are some fluctuations between the number of males and females educated, the male and female upper secondary school completion rates follow very similar levels, suggesting that progress had been made in closing this gap, prior to 2000.

Figure I. Labour Force Participation Rate and Upper Secondary School Completion Rate by Gender, 2000-2020, South America

Notes: Data for both variables are averaged for all 10 countries for each year in the 20-year period.

As my hypotheses predict, a reduction in the (average) gender gap in employment is negatively correlated with (average) economic growth, as shown in Figure II. The gender gap in employment, measured as the difference between male and female labour force participation divided by total labour force participation is steadily decreasing over time in South America, meaning employment is becoming more gender equal. Meanwhile, GDPPC has seen an upward trend.

Figure II. LFPRRate Gender Gap Index and GDPPC over time for 2000-2020, South America
 Notes: Data averaged out for all 10 countries for each year. GDPPC runs from 2000-2020 for each country for each year. Meanwhile data on labour force participation rate is available for each country for each year up until 2019.

Looking more closely at GDPPC, its trend over time slightly fluctuates although this is largely related to various economic crises that hit South America. GDPPC initially decreased from 2000 to 2002 because of a recession that primarily affected Argentina. This recession came due to ineffective fiscal policy, slow structural reform and a financial sector collapse due to inefficient credit markets (International Monetary Fund, 2003). GDPPC then increased over time from 2003 with a decline in 2008 likely due to the global financial crisis. The decline seen in 2014 and the consecutive years are likely a result of the Brazilian economic crisis. This recession occurred because of a fall in the commodity prices for iron ore and raw sugar, which are Brazil’s biggest exports (European Central Bank, 2016). As Brazil is one of the largest economies in the region, this influenced other countries’ GDPPC because many relied on Brazil’s demand for their exports (Pearson Institute for International Economics, 2016). Finally, the decline in 2020 is likely a result of the global Covid-19 pandemic.

Over time, the gender gap in education fluctuates (shown in Figure III), however, this is partially due missing data points that have arisen for reasons already

Figure III. SchoolingRate Gender Gap Index and GDPPC over time, 2000-2020, South America
 Notes: Data averaged out for all 10 countries for each year. GDPPC runs from 2000-2020 for each country for each year. Unfortunately, due to data issues, there is no data for 2000 and 2002 for any lower secondary school completion rate (education gender gap). Also, for 2001, the data is only available for Argentina and Bolivia.

discussed. However, although the relationship for the educational gender gap is not as correlated with GDPPC as that of the employment gender gap; it also depicts a relatively negative relationship, meaning as the gender gap in upper secondary school completion rate decreases over time, the GDPPC tends to increase.

The highest earning country per capita for the period 2000-2020 is Uruguay, with an average GDPPC of \$11464.53 (Figure IV and V). Meanwhile, the lowest was Bolivia with an average of \$2074.76 GDPPC.

Several countries have a negative SchoolingRate, implying that females have a higher level of education than males on average. These countries include Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Uruguay, and Venezuela. Also, for the countries that have a positive educational gender gap, the gap is relatively small when compared to the gender gap in employment (LFPRRate), meaning that in the region, there is higher gender inequality in employment than education. For the gender gaps in

employment, all are positive and considerably large, meaning women work significantly less than men in South America.

Figure IV. SchoolingRate Education Gender Gap and GDPPC by Country, 2000-2020.

Notes: The average GDPPC and average SchoolingRate for each country over the 20-year period from 2000-2020 is plotted onto this scatter chart.

On average for the sample period, the least equal country in terms of education is Uruguay with a gap of -0.213 (Figure IV). As it is negative this gender gap favours females. Uruguay is followed by Peru with an education gap of 0.183 which is gender biased against females. Interestingly, Peru is the most equal country in terms of employment (0.217) (Figure V). This is an unexpected finding as an increase in education equality is thought to increase the employment equality as those who better educated individuals are more likely to seek employment (IZA World of Labor, 2016). Therefore, in terms of my hypothesis, Peru as a country supports hypothesis two but goes against hypothesis one.

Uruguay has the highest GDPPC and is the second most equal country in terms of employment (0.245), thus providing some support for hypothesis one. On the other hand, the most equal country in terms of education is Ecuador (0.019) closely followed by Colombia (-0.023), although in terms of GDPPC these are some of the lowest income countries, which also goes against hypothesis two. The country with the highest gender gap in employment is Venezuela, with a gap of 0.444, whilst having the 5th highest GDPPC of all countries in the sample.

An interesting country to look at is Chile, with the second highest average GDPPC, it is one of the most developed countries in the region and has one of the lowest educational gender-based inequalities, whilst at the same time it has the highest level of gender inequality in employment. This highlights the potential issue of reverse causality in this study. One possible explanation for this could be that as GDPPC increases, females do not need to work as the husbands' incomes are sufficient for survival (Psacharopoulos and Tzannatos, 1993).

Figure V. LFPRRate Employment Gender Gap and GDPPC by Country, 2000-2020.

Notes: The average GDPPC and average SchoolingRate for each country over the 20-year period from 2000-2020 is plotted onto this scatter chart.

When looking at Figures IV and V we see a slightly different relationship to what was shown by Figures II and III. When plotting the countries' average GDPPC against average years of schooling, we see that the poorest countries are countries that have a high educational gender gap favouring males and as the gender gap shrinks, GDPPC grows. Furthermore, the richest countries in the region are those that have a gender gap where more females are educated. In terms of employment, the relationship is not as clear. However, the richer countries tend to have a slightly higher gender inequality level on average (as shown in Figure V).

4.2 OLS Regression Results

Table II: OLS Regression Results (2000-2020)

			(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	
			Model with added controls	Model with country FE	Model with time FE	Model with country and time FE	
SchoolingRate	-2.810*** (0.386)	-2.747*** (0.312)	-0.983** (0.491)	-0.370 (1.037)	-1.949*** (0.397)	-0.550 (0.388)	
LFPRRate	-1.787*** (0.670)	-1.616*** (0.437)	-0.951*** (0.380)	-1.844** (0.870)	-0.871*** (0.279)	0.577* (0.341)	
Fertility			-1.147*** (0.151)	-2.685*** (0.363)	-0.866*** (0.115)	-0.719*** (0.232)	
Exports			0.012 (0.008)	0.007 (0.006)	-0.018*** (0.005)	-0.019*** (0.004)	
Log(pop)			-0.105* (0.059)	-5.109*** (1.321)	0.002*** (0.045)	-4.690*** (1.173)	
EducationExpenditure			0.102** (0.051)	0.241*** (0.050)	-0.002 (0.039)	-0.016 (0.026)	
Country FE	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Time FE	No	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
N	87	87	87	87	87	87	87
R squared	0.331	0.083	0.398	0.721	0.906	0.886	0.986

*Significant at 10% level, ** Significant at 5% level, ***Significant at 1% level. Robust standard errors in parentheses.

Notes: This table provides results on the effect various variables have on economic growth. (1) looks at the effect of gender gaps in education on economic growth. (2) looks at the effect of a gender gap in employment on economic growth. (3) looks at the effects of both gender gaps in education and employment on economic growth. (4) looks at the same as (3) with the inclusion of controls for Fertility rate, Exports, the natural logarithm of population and education expenditure. (5) also controls for country fixed effects country. (6) also control for time fixed effects. (7) controls for both country and time fixed effects.

As shown earlier in Table I, the standard deviations (SD) for both gender gap index variables are close to 0.10 (0.129 for the education gender gap index and 0.094 for employment). In the analysis, in Table II, models (1)-(4) show that a higher gender gap in education and employment reduces economic growth and the results are statistically significant at 1% level. Model (1) addresses only the gender gap in education, and suggests that an increase in the gender gap in education index by the SD (0.10) reduces GDPPC by 28.1% and model (2) states that an increase in LFPRRate by the SD reduces GDPPC by 17.9%, both are statistically significant at the 1% level. This suggests that the more gender equal a country in terms of both employment

and education, the more it will grow. When looking at them both together, it appears the educational gender gap still has a slightly larger effect on economic growth than the employment gender gap, whilst both negatively affect economic growth. Again, when adding in controls for fertility, exports, $\log(\text{pop})$ and education expenditure the influence of a gender gap in education has a larger impact than employment. However, the coefficients for both independent variables is smaller with the controls added. An increase by the SD in the LFPRRate is now considered to reduce economic growth by 9.51% (at the 1% significance level), while a SchoolingRate increase by the SD reduces economic growth by 9.83% (at the 5% significance level). This is because the control factors can now explain part of the changes in economic growth, and all are significant at 10% level except for exports. When comparing the results to that of similar studies, they were found to be consistent (Klasen, 2000; Baerlocher et al, 2018; Cabeza-Garcia, Del Brio and Oscanoa-Victorio, 2018). As is to be expected, in consistency with the existing findings mentioned above, fertility and population growth have a negative effect on economic growth whilst exports and education expenditure have a positive effect.

In models (5)-(7) country and time FE are considered, both individually and together. Controlling for country FE (5), shows a negative relationship. However, the magnitudes suggest that a higher gender gap in employment now has more of an effect on GDP (where an increase in LFPRRate by 0.1 reduces GDP by 18.4%) than the gender gap in education (where a 0.1 increase in the gender gap reduces GDP by 3.7%). Although, the statistical significance is reduced. LFPRRate is now only statistically significant at the 5% level while SchoolingRate is not at any level. When controlling for time FE (6), both independent variables are statistically significant at the 1% level, along with all variables except education spending. Similarly to the previous models there is a negative relationship between GDPPC and the gender gaps in both education and employment, meaning the model continues to remain consistent with existing findings and my hypotheses.

A notable conclusion that can be drawn from (7) is the sign change on LFPRRate, suggesting that when time and country FE are considered together, an increase of 0.10 in the education gender gap leads to a 5.8% increase in economic

growth, but an increase by 0.10 in the employment gender gap index leads to a 5.5% decrease in economic growth. By controlling for country and time FE together, the variation in the dependent variable is isolated to within each country, thus for some countries in some years, gender inequality leads to improved economic growth. This inclusion also affects the significance of the indicators. The *SchoolingRate* is not significant at any level (like when only country FE are considered) and *LFPRRate* is significant at the 10% level only. Thus, this suggests that controlling for country FE makes the effect of these gender gaps on economic growth, especially that of education, less clear.

4.3 Heterogeneity

4.3.1 Heterogeneity between Countries

In the OLS regression, it was found that gender inequality in employment led to improved economic growth when controlling for country and time FE in conjunction. To try to establish what is causing this, quantile regression was performed. Quantile regression assesses the relationship between the variables at different parts of the distribution, where the distribution is ordered in GDPPC values i.e. values for each year for each country. For example, the first tercile will measure the relationship for the third of countries that have the lowest GDPPC. The second tercile will measure GDPPC for the lowest two thirds of countries by GDPPC. Using this method assesses where the heterogeneity comes from and whether it is poor countries that are driving the positive relationship between the employment gender gap and economic growth or the richer countries.

Table III: Quantile Regression, 2000-2020

	(1)	(2)	(3)
	Model with control variables	Model with controls and Time FE	Model with Country and Time FE
<i>1st Tercile</i>			
LFPRRate	-1.837*** (0.719)	-1.126 (0.844)	0.467 (0.537)
SchoolingRate	-0.529 (0.444)	-1.536 (1.016)	-0.198 (0.774)
R squared	0.465	0.683	0.890
<i>2nd Tercile</i>			
LFPRRate	-1.329*** (0.502)	-0.772* (0.447)	0.115 (0.654)
SchoolingRate	-1.266** (0.592)	-1.534** (0.632)	-0.831 (0.804)
R squared	0.546	0.697	0.903
Controls Fixed	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country FE	No	No	Yes
Time FE	No	Yes	Yes
N	87	87	87

*Significant at 10% level, ** Significant at 5% level, ***Significant at 1% level. Robust standard errors in parentheses. Notes: (1) fertility, exports, log(pop) and education expenditure included as control variables. (2) control variables included as well as time fixed effects. (3) country and time fixed effects are included in conjunction, as well as control variables.

The results in (1) and (2) in Table III are consistent with the findings from the OLS regression displayed in Table II, which displays a negative relationship between the gender gap variables and GDPPC. Among the poorer countries in (1) an increase in the index by the SD (0.10) in the gender gap in employment reduces economic growth by 18.4% and among the richer countries the same increase reduces economic growth by 13.3%. Additionally, among the poorer countries an increase by 0.10 in the educational gender gap index results in a 5.3% decrease in economic growth but in the poorer country results in a 12.7% decline in growth. Thus, while the relationship is stronger among the poorer countries than the richer in terms of

employment, the richer countries are more affected by a decline in the educational gender equality than the poorer countries. Thus as a country gets richer, a gender gap in education reduces GDPPC by more and a gender gap in employment reduces GDPPC by less. However, the significance changes under quantile regression. In column 1 the employment gender gap is statistically significant at the 1% level, as in OLS, but the education gender gap is not statistically significant in the 1st tercile and significant only at the 5% level in the 2nd tercile. Therefore, we cannot assume the effect of the gender gap in education is different from zero, suggesting that the education gender gap is less influential when countries are poor than when they are richer. When controlling for time FE, the size of the coefficients for LFPR decrease regardless of the GDPPC of the country meanwhile the SchoolingRate coefficient increases. From this we can infer that the time FE variable accounts for some of the impact of LFPRRate on GDPPC and leads SchoolingRate to be more impactful. This could be because of certain policies or general economic conditions in the region. Again, these results are only statistically significant in the 2nd tercile, meaning we can conclude that there are more influential factors affecting the GDPPC in the poorer countries.

Column 3 of Table IV shows the instance when country and time FE are controlled for. As shown, the employment gender gap is positive for both tercile values suggesting that as the employment gender gap increases, GDDPPC increases. However, the coefficient reduces in size as the countries get richer, thus suggesting that the positive relationship is driven more by the poorer countries. But, the results are not statistically significant for either terciles.

4.3.2 Heterogeneity across the Years

It has been found by previous studies that recessions generally affect men more than women (Engemann and Wall, 2009; Hoynes, Miller and Schaller, 2012; McKay et al, 2013) as men are generally employed in manufacturing and industrial sectors which tend to follow the cyclical pattern. Whilst women are more likely to work in the service or domestic sector. To look at whether this has occurred and whether the relationship between economic growth and gender gaps has changed OLS regressions were analysed for specific periods of crisis; the Global financial crisis

(GFC), 2008-2010 and the Brazilian Recession (BR) 2014-2016. In 2009 every country, except Bolivia and Venezuela contracted and from 2014-2016, every country in the sample portrayed a negative GDPPC growth rate (World Bank, 2022).

Table IV: OLS Regression results during period of crises, 2008-2010 and 2014-2016

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	GFC Model with Controls	GFC Model with Country FE	BR Model with Controls	BR Model with Country FE
SchoolingRate	-1.134 (0.809)	-2.256 (1.721)	-1.001 (0.978)	-0.192 (3.048)
LFPRRate	-2.246** (0.918)	0.047 (4.900)	-0.690 (0.902)	-3.486** (1.414)
Fertility	-0.642** (0.226)	-1.902 (2.807)	-0.923** (0.387)	-7.346 (5.716)
Exports	0.044*** (0.014)	-0.012 (0.049)	0.005 (0.016)	0.007 (0.010)
Log(pop)	0.057 (0.166)	11.345** (4.410)	-0.120 (0.125)	-27.799* (13.025)
EducationExpenditure	0.344*** (0.110)	-0.383 (0.379)	-0.014 (0.058)	-0.088 (0.068)
Country FE	No	Yes	No	Yes
R squared	0.939	0.994	0.789	0.989
N	14	14	19	19

*Significant at 10% level, ** Significant at 5% level, ***Significant at 1% level. Robust standard errors in parentheses.

Notes: (1) looks at the model including the control variables as listed for GFC. (2) includes country FE as well for GFC. (3) includes the controls as listed for BR. (4) also including country FE for BR.

Firstly, as shown in Figure I, for the region there is no obvious decline in the LFPR for either males or females during either period of crises. The female LFPR declines by 1.8% from 2008 to 2010 and increases by more than 10% during the 2014-2016 period. Meanwhile, male LFPR declines by 0.7% over the GFC and decreases by less than 0.5% in the 2014-2016 crisis. This suggests that South America is generally inconsistent with the findings mentioned above. In terms of education,

both genders follow a very similar trend. Education responds differently in each recession period. In the GFC, the education rate falls in 2009 for both genders but picks up again in 2010. In the Brazilian recession, the education of both genders is increasing throughout.

From Table IV, the *SchoolingRate* is negatively correlated with economic growth. However, during these focus periods, it is not statistically significant at any level for both the key crisis periods. This suggests that during the recessions the relationship between the gender gap in education and economic growth became less clear. This is likely due to economic growth being largely affected by the other factors in the economy at the time. As previously discussed, *GDPPC* was decreasing during these specific times, which could have affected the relationship.

Table IV shows that the models exhibit a negative and significant (at the 5% level) relationship between *GDPPC* and *LFPRRate* for GFC, in (1). However, after the inclusion of country FE (2), this relationship becomes positive and loses its statistical significance, thus suggesting that, although difficult to confirm, when the deviation of each individual country is controlled for separately a higher inequality within employment leads to higher economic growth. For the 2014 recession, the *LFPRRate* portrays a negative relationship with *GDPPC* regardless of whether country FE are controlled for, but the result becomes statistically significant in the FE model. This suggests that when there is a rise in the *LFPRRate* by 0.10 economic growth falls by 34.9% during the Brazilian recession. However, this result could be because the gender gap has widened at the same time economic growth has reduced due to the economic downturn, therefore again suggesting the issue of reverse causality is present.

4.4 GMM Estimation

Finally, to address the reverse causality issues aforementioned, GMM estimation is performed. This will allow us to determine causal links between the gender gap variables and the influence they have on *GDPPC*. The results are outlined in Table V.

Table V: GMM estimate, 2000-2020

	(1)
LFPRRate	-0.862** (0.325)
SchoolingRate	-1.407*** (0.402)
Fertility	0.239 (0.196)
Exports	-0.001 (0.005)
Log(pop)	0.033 (0.039)
Education Expenditure	0.023 (0.045)
Lagged GDPPC 1 Year	0.910*** (0.147)
Lagged GDPPC 2 Years	-0.262* (0.135)
N	46
A-Bond Test AR(1)	0.004
A-Bond Test AR(2)	0.135***
Sargan Test	0.315***

*Significant at 10% level, ** Significant at 5% level, ***Significant at 1% level. Robust standard errors in parentheses.
Notes: (1) depicts the model when a lag of GDPPC of 1 and 2 years is included.

In Table V, the coefficients on the gender gap variables for education and employment are negative and statistically significant. The education gender gap is statistically significant at the 1% level, meanwhile the employment gender gap is at the 5% level. This means that once the reverse causality issue is removed, the gender gaps in education and employment both have a negative effect on economic growth. As these gender gaps in education and employment increase by 0.10, they will lead to a fall in GDPPC by 8.6% and 14.1% respectively. However, none of the control variables in the model are statistically significant.

In terms of the tests, the A-Bond tests identify whether there is autocorrelation amongst the variables with the null hypothesis indicating that there is no autocorrelation. In the GMM model we fail to reject AR(2) at the 1% level meaning it can be concluded that there is no autocorrelation in the model. The Sargan test checks the validity of the model and ensures the model is correctly specified, with the null hypothesis confirming these to be the case. Therefore, in these results the null hypothesis cannot be rejected at the 1% level in (1), meaning the model is correct and valid.

4.5 Robustness

Two potential aspects of contention with this study are the choice of measurement of the gender gap and the way economic growth is measured.

An alternative way to construct a variable that measures a gender gap would be to mimic how the gender pay gap is measured in the UK (Office for National Statistics, 2022) using the difference between male and female education or employment indexed to male education or employment.

$$\text{Male Indexed Employment Rate} = \frac{\text{Male LFPR} - \text{Female LFPR}}{\text{Male LFPR}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Male Indexed Education Rate} = \frac{\text{Male Educational Attainment} - \text{Female Educational Attainment}}{\text{Male Educational Attainment}} \quad (6)$$

In the literature, others use GDPPC growth as a measure and as a robustness check (Ghosh and Ramanyake, 2018) rather than using GDPPC as used in my study.

The study will be assumed to be robust if the relationship between the independent variables and the measure of economic growth is the same across the models and the model in my original OLS regression.

Table VI: Robustness Checks

	Male Indexed Rate				Growth of GDPPC as Dependent			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Education Gender Gap	-1.027** (0.459)	-0.843 (1.108)	-1.941*** (0.369)	-0.599 (0.392)	-73.340*** (23.782)	-43.005 (54.395)	-32.135 (19.811)	-79.461 (53.581)
Employment Gender Gap	-1.272*** (0.485)	-2.727** (1.174)	-1.007*** (0.355)	0.800* (0.481)	2.594 (16.668)	-191.0*** (62.648)	-18.733 (11.711)	23.256 (46.553)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country FE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Time FE	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
N	87	87	87	87	58	58	58	58
R squared	0.727	0.907	0.892	0.986	0.309	0.532	0.839	0.862

*Significant at 10% level, ** Significant at 5% level, ***Significant at 1% level. Robust standard errors in parentheses.

Notes: Columns (1), (2), (3) and (4) display the models where the male indexed rate is used as a robustness check. Columns (5), (6), (7) and (8) display the models where the Growth in GDPPC is used as the dependent variable. (1) and (5) include the control variables, (2) and (6) include controls and country fixed effects, (3) and (7) include controls time fixed effects and (4) and (8) include country and time fixed effects as well as control variables.

Columns 1, 2, 3 and 4 use the male indexed rates and prove a similar relationship where both the education and employment gender gaps have a negative relationship with economic growth in all models, except in (4), where country and time FE are controlled for in conjunction. In (4), the education gender gap has a negative relationship with economic growth, meanwhile the employment gender gap has a positive relationship. This reflects the same findings as in the original study. Also (excluding (1) when no FE are controlled for), although the magnitudes differ slightly from the original model; the magnitude of each variable compared to the other remains consistent, i.e. when the SchoolingRate has a larger magnitude than the LFPRRate in the original model, it also has a larger magnitude in the robustness check. The significance levels are also identical to the original model, where if the coefficients are statistically significant at the 1% level, this is matched in the robustness check with a significance at the 1% level.

In terms of using GDPPC growth as a robustness check, we again see similar relationships between the gender gap variables and economic growth for each model. The coefficients largely depict the same negative relationship as in the OLS study, excluding the employment gender gap when country and time FE are controlled for (8), which depicts a positive relationship, the same as in the original

study. Although the magnitudes are very large in this check, they are similar to the original model in the sense that when the *SchoolingRate* has a larger influence than *LFPRRate* in the original model it also does in this check. However, differing from the initial study there is a positive relationship with GDPPC growth and the employment gender gap (*LFPRRate*) in model 5, where no FE are included. However, the result for this is statistically insignificant.

Overall, the results in Table VI are similar in their signs, magnitudes and significance to the original OLS results (Table II). From this it can be concluded that our main results are not affected by the choice of measure for either the dependent or independent variables.

5. Conclusion

This study has analysed whether there is a relationship between economic growth and gender gaps within education and employment in South America. There are several findings produced by this study. The descriptive results find that generally as economic growth increases, the gender gaps in employment and education reduce over time. However, it can be said that the richer countries are less gender equal than the poorer ones in terms of employment. However, in terms of the gender gap in education the richer countries have a negative gender gap, meaning females are more educated than males. Meanwhile, the poorer countries experience educational gender inequality that is detrimental to the females.

It can be concluded that a negative relationship is established between the gender gaps and economic growth. Having said this, when country and time FE were both controlled for in the OLS model the effect of the gender gaps is more ambiguous, and a positive relationship between economic growth and the gender gap in employment was discovered. Thus when the variation in economic growth is isolated to a specific country at specific points in time, an increase in the gender inequality in employment is matched with an increase in economic growth. It was then discovered through quantile regression that this positive result was stronger among the poorer countries. Meanwhile, the relationship between economic growth and gender inequality within education, although always negative, is stronger among the richer countries.

Using GMM to overcome the issue of simultaneity and reverse causality, a negative effect is established, with higher gender gaps in education and employment reducing economic growth. However, the effect on GDPPC of an increase in the gender gap in education is larger than the effect of an increase in the gender gap in employment of the same size. These arguably causal results are no longer affected by the reverse causality or unobserved heterogeneity initially present in the model.

Thus, to improve economic growth South American countries could focus on reducing gender inequality within education and employment. Specifically, the poorer countries such as Bolivia, Paraguay and Ecuador should focus on reducing

gender inequality within employment while the richer countries such as Uruguay, Chile and Argentina should focus on reducing gender inequality within education.

[Word Count: 9929]

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7. Appendix

Table A1: Variables included in the Model, and their Descriptions.

Variable	Description
Dependent Variable	
logGDPPC	Natural logarithm GDP in current US\$ divided by population in that year. It is also a standard measurement for growth.
Independent Variable	
SchoolingRate	% of individuals that completed education at a level at least upper secondary school. The rate is calculated by $\frac{\text{Male educational attainment} - \text{Female educational attainment}}{\text{Total educational attainment}}$
LFPRRate	The gender gap in employment measured using labour force participation calculated as $\frac{\text{Male LFPR} - \text{Female LFPR}}{\text{Total LFPR}}$ Where labour force participation is % of total population within the labour force for ages 15-64.
Control Variables	
Fertility	Average births per woman
Log(pop)	Natural logarithm of population for each country.
Exports	The amount exported of goods and services, as a % of GDP.
Education Expenditure	Government expenditure as % GDP.

Table A2: Country Level Data, 2000-2020

	Argentina	Bolivia	Brazil	Chile	Colombia	Ecuador	Paraguay	Peru	Uruguay	Venezuela
logGDPPC	2.124	0.608	1.952	2.321	1.579	1.409	1.296	1.436	2.302	2.038
GDPPC	9225.64	2074.76	7854.13	11086.95	5274.88	4462.86	4196.11	4654.54	11464.53	6209.48
YoY Growth	0.040	0.044	0.050	0.045	0.044	0.060	0.055	0.057	0.039	0.072
GDDPC (2000)	7666.52	977.34	3726.81	5097.11	2547.14	1451.53	1728.34	1941.32	6932.47	4795.40
GDPPC (2020)	8585.69	3068.81	6794.52	13094.46	5307.22	5645.20	5353.35	6056.34	15619.54	-
Growth over period*	0.982	3.474	1.621	4.276	2.616	2.871	2.739	4.070	4.236	5.493
SchoolingRate	-0.093	0.179	-0.088	0.031	-0.023	0.019	0.027	0.183	-0.223	-0.143
LFPRRate	0.354	0.281	0.325	0.439	0.356	0.428	0.383	0.217	0.245	0.444
Fertility	2.362	3.267	1.883	1.840	2.075	2.663	2.809	2.519	2.051	2.491
Exports	17.974	32.747	13.160	34.490	16.431	26.108	40.654	24.336	25.769	29.0178
Education Expenditure	4.816	8.316	5.291	4.294	4.342	4.353	3.241	3.536	3.696	3.106
RD	0.506	0.254	1.122	0.358	0.222	0.245	0.090	0.116	0.360	0.243
Labour Force (% Population)	44.7%	45.9%	47.5%	45.3%	49.0%	45.0%	46.5%	40.7%	49.0%	43.3%
Population	41,095,123	10,239,745	195,757,018	17,096,540	44,807,541	15,015,309	5,826,911	29,528,508	3,359,717	28,125,752

*Growth over period is calculated as % change in GDP in 2020 compared to 2000. YoY Growth is calculated as the growth rate of GDPPC from year to year.

Notes: All other variables are means calculated for each individual country over the period 2000-2020.